

SYED FARID ALATAS

THE *ṬARĪQAT AL-'ALAWIYYAH* AND THE EMERGENCE
OF THE SHI'Ī SCHOOL IN INDONESIA AND MALAYSIA*

Introduction

The recent emergence and current development of the Imami Shi'ī school in Indonesia and Malaysia can only be understood against the backdrop of the early history of the *Šī'ah*, as well as that of the history of the Islamization of the Malay-Indonesian Archipelago. The common factor that binds these three historical processes together in a remarkable case of "conversion" within Islam is the *'alawīyyah* sufi order (*al-ṭarīqah al-'alawīyyah*).

The *ṭarīqah al-'alawīyyah* is the path of the *Sādat Banī 'alawīyyah*. The *Sādah al-'alawīyyah* (sing. *sayyid*), of the Shafi'ī *madhab* (school of jurisprudence), originate from the Ḥaḍramawt, Yemen and played a major role in the Islamization of East Africa, Southern India, and the Malay-Indonesian Archipelago. The *Sayyids* of Ḥaḍramawt share a common history with the Shi'ī school and to some extent it is this commonality that caused Shi'ī elements and tendencies among the descendants of Hadrami *Sādat* émigrés in the Malay-Indonesian Archipelago to surface, particularly after the Iranian revolution of 1978. Today, the Hadrami *Sayyids* of the Malay-Indonesian world continue to play a role in the religious life of the region. With this in mind, it is important and interesting to observe that the *'alawīyyah 'ulamā'* in particular and community in general is becoming differentiated into a number of orientations vis a vis the Shi'ī school. To date, the literature on Islam in Indonesia, Malaysia and the rest of the region has not taken note of this phenomenon, with the exception of a few journal articles and a handful of newspaper and magazine items. Even then, these works falsely labour under the assumption that the rise of the Shi'ī school in the region is symptomatic of the current wave of Islamic fundamentalism, being a result of the establishment of a Shi'ī republic in Iran in 1979. It would be more accurate to say that the Iranian revolution had resulted in whatever Shi'ī tendencies that had already existed among the *'Alawīyyūn* of the Malay world being articulated with greater clarity, fervour and sense of mission.

* - This essay on the Shi'ī school in Indonesia and Malaysia is merely a preface to a larger work and is based on materials gathered during an exploratory two weeks field trip in Indonesia during the summer of 1993. Funding for this trip was provided by the Institute of Southeast Asian Studies, Singapore.

The purpose of this study is to examine the emergence of the Shi'i school in the Malay-Indonesian archipelago, in the context of the origins and early history of Shi'i Islam as well as that of the Islamization of the Malay world.

The next section on the origins and development of Shi'i Islam touches upon various aspects of the political history of early Islam, the development of the five legal schools (*madāhib*), as well as the pendulum rise of the Shi'i state in Iran.

This is followed by a discussion on the question of the principle divergences between the Sunni and Shi'i schools, not only in terms of jurisprudence but the rational sciences (*al-'ulūm al-'aqliyyah*) and political theory as well.

The discussion moves on to the *ṭarīqah al-'alawiyyah*, tracing its origins in Ḥaḍramawt, and its spread to the Malay world by the *Sayyids* of Ḥaḍramawt. It is also here that I elaborate on the belief system (*'aqīdah*) of the Hadrami *Sayyids* (i.e. the *ṭarīqah*), and locate the *'Alawiyūn* historically and doctrinally vis à vis the Sunni-Shi'i divide.

The final section then shifts to a discussion on the rise of *Imāmī Šī'ah* among the *'Alawiyūn* of the Malay world both before and after the Iranian revolution of 1978.

This section illustrates the various orientations toward the Shi'i school among the *'Alawiyūn*. The question of adherence to the Sunni or Shi'i schools refers to more than schools of jurisprudence but to political theory, historical consciousness, philosophy, theology and sufism, but this argument is not developed in the present essay.

The Origins and Development of Šī'ah Islam

The division of the *ummah* into its Sunni and Shi'i branches emerged originally as a result of irreconcilable political differences over the succession of the Prophet Muḥammad (peace be upon Him) and the leadership of the community. It is only much later that further differences in terms of belief systems, philosophy and jurisprudence emerged. These will be treated in the next section.

There are several theories on the rise and early development of Islam, their propounders being Muslims as well orientalists, historical materialists, and a number of other Western scholars.

The Muslim explanations of the origins of early Islam broadly fall into two groups, the standard Sunni¹ and Shi'i² versions. In addition, there are also critical accounts that are based on both Sunni and Shi'i sources.³

1 – al-Baḡdādī, Abū Maṅṣūr, *al-Farq bayn al-firaq*, al-Qāhirah, 1948; Ibn Ḥāzim, Abū Muḥammad 'A., *al-Faṣl fī 'l-milal wa 'l-aḥwā' wa 'l-niḥal*, al-Qāhirah, 1347h.; al-Šahrastānī, M., *al-Milal wa 'l-niḥal*, al-Qāhirah, 1961; al-Balāḍūrī, A., *Futūḥ al-bul-dān*, Hitti, Ph.K. (trans.), *Origins of the Islamic State*, New York, 1916; Ibn Sa'd, M.,

Apart from these standard Muslim perspectives, modern scholars of Islam have also attempted to account for the rise and early development of Islam. Many of these theories locate the rise of Islam around the theme of Mecca as a centre of caravan trade in the Arabian peninsula.⁴

Whatever the role of trade, ecology and various sociological factors in the rise and subsequent development of Islam, it is equally plausible to view these developments in Khaldunian terms, for which the concept of 'aşabiyyah is of paramount importance.⁵

The eventual rise of the Umayyah dynasty left the Šī'ah (party) of Imām 'Alī, a group that gathered around 'Alī and his descendants, in the opposition. The revolt of Imām al-Ḥusayn against Mu'āwiyah's successor, Yazīd, and his tragic destruction in the battle of Karbalā' (muḥarram 61/October 680) signified the end of anti-Umayyah activism of the Šī'ah. The fourth, fifth and sixth Imāms, that is, 'Alī Zayn al-'Ābidīn, Muḥammad al-Bāqir and Ġa'far al-Šādiq retreated to Madina and diverted their attention to the development and codification of the *turāt* (heritage). In fact, it is the last who elaborated on the doctrine of the *imāmah*, giving it its final form. The *imāmah* is an office bestowed by God upon a chosen person from among the descendants of the Prophet through 'Alī and Fāṭimah (*Ahl al-Bayt*).⁶

Nevertheless, the Šī'ah never controlled a state till the emergence of the Safavids in 907/1501 and it was only in 1979 that the *arbāb-i 'amā'im* (religious institution) captured state power.

Sunni and Shi'i: Principle Divergences

Many Muslim scholars and laymen alike are often quick to point out that the differences between the *ahl al-sunnah wa 'l-ġamā'ah* and the Šī'ah are minor and that both groups co-exist in Muslim brotherhood (*uḥūwat*

Kitāb al-ṭabaqāt al-kubrā, Bayrūt, 1957; al-Ṭabarī, Abū Ġa'far, *Tarīḥ al-rusul wa 'l-mulūk*, de Goeje, M.J. et alii (eds.), Leiden, 1879-1901.

2 – al-Mas'ūdī, 'A., *Murūġ al-ḍahab*, Bayrūt, 1966; al-Ya'qūbī, A., *al-Ta'rīḥ*, 1960.

3 – See, for example, Jafri, S.H.M., *Origins and Early Development of Shi'a Islam*, Qum, Ansariyan Publications, nd.

4 – Engineer, A.A., *The Origins and Development of Islam*, Kuala Lumpur, 1990; Sharma, A., "Max Weber's Concept of Routinization of Charisma and Abu Bakar", in: *Hamdard Islamicus*, 4, 119, p. 65-69; Watt, W.M., *Muhammad at Mecca*, Oxford, 1953; *id.*, *Muhammad at Medina*, Oxford, 1956; *id.*, *Muhammad, Prophet and Statesman*, Oxford, 1964; Aswad, B., "Social and Ecological Aspects in the Origin of the Islamic State", in: *Papers of the Michigan Academy of Science, Arts and Letters*, 48 (1963), p. 419-442; Bousquet, G.H., "Observations Sociologiques sur les origines de l'Islam", in: *Studia Islamica*, 2 (1954), p. 61-87; Crone, P., *Meccan Trade and the Rise of Islam*, Oxford, 1987.

5 – Ibn Ḥaldūn, *Muqaddimat Ibn Ḥaldūn*, Bayrūt, 1981.

6 – Jafri, *Origins*, cit., p. 290.

al-islāmiyyah). While this form of brotherhood is true historically as well as at the present, this must not lead us to underestimate the differences in philosophy and outlook between the two.

More often than not, the Sunni-Shi'i divide is perceived in terms of jurisprudence and the principles of jurisprudence and in fact, this is the area where the differences between the two are the least. Thus, it is important not to reduce the Sunni and *Ši'ah* to schools of jurisprudence (*madāhib*) as if they differ along only these lines.

In fact the principle divergences between the Sunni and *Ši'ah* exist across the whole spectrum of the belief system. While the initial differences concerned notions of justice and the question of succession, the two groups that evolved separately as a result of these differences developed distinct traditions in political theory, philosophy, theology, mysticism, and jurisprudence.

The *'aqīdah* can be utilized as an organizing principle with which we may develop comparative dimensions to appreciate Sunni-Shi'i differences. In a more restricted sense, *'aqīdah* refers to article of faith, the formulation of doctrine or dogma, or even a formula that seeks to define the stance of a scholar or individual, usually with respect to theological issues. In a more general sense, *'aqīdah* refers to epistemological and other philosophical issues and, therefore, approximates the total outlook or belief system of an individual or school. This would of course, be in keeping with the modern rendition of *'aqīdah* as ideology, at least in the Arabic language.

The Sunni and Shi'i *'aqā'id*, therefore, differ across the whole spectrum of doctrines, concepts, theories, and rulings.

Of paramount importance is the question of historical consciousness. The event of the Saqīfah, the murder of Sayyidnā 'Alī, and the tragedy of Karbalā' are historical events about which Muslims cannot be neutral. The average Sunni is unaware of these events and, therefore, lacks an historical dimension to the question of justice and truth in Islam. What has prevailed as the "truth" is that which is held by the majority (*ahl al-ḡamā'ah*). The degree to which this historically early majority were *ahl al-sunnah* as well is a matter of contention from the Shi'i point of view. The proclamation of majority status by those claiming to adhere to the *sunnah* of the Prophet resulted in the definition of historical reality through silence and falsification, it has been claimed. As standard Sunni interpretations of early Muslim history took root, their legitimacy was boosted by the fact that these views were held by the majority. This reminds us of Alexis de Tocqueville's theory of democracy where he spoke of the tyranny and degradation of the majority.

The different notions of justice and truth are also reflected in the political theories to which the Sunnis and Shi'is subscribe, that is, the theory of the caliphate (*hilāfah*) on the one hand and the theories of imamate (*imāmah*) and *wilāyat al-faqīh* on the other.

There are, of course, the well-known differences in the areas of jurisprudence and its principles, concerning the five schools as well as the question of *madhab Ahl al-Bayt*.

Concerning the rational and intellectual sciences (*al-‘ulūm al-‘aqliyyah*), namely *kalām* (theology), *falsafah* (philosophy), and *taṣawwuf* (sufism), the Sunni and *Šī‘ah* fall into different categories as well.

In philosophy, the Sunni tend to be *maššā‘ūn* (Peripatetic, deductionist), whereas the *Šī‘ah* tend to be *išrāqīs* (illuminationists), combining rational deduction (*istidlāl*) and demonstration (*burhān*) with asceticism, mystical experience, purification of the soul, and experiential wisdom (*ḥikmat al-ḍawqī*).

In theology, the Sunnis tend to be either *mu‘tazilah* or followers of al-Aš‘arī. The *Šī‘ah* belong to their own school of theology, while borrowing from the *mu‘tazilah*.

In *taṣawwuf*, the *ṭarīqah* is seen by the Sunnis as *‘irfān*, involving a near total rejection of rational deduction while the *Šī‘ah* combine rational deduction and the Sufī spiritual path (*ṭarīqah*).

From Imām to Sayyid: The Ṭarīqah al-‘Alawīyyah, the Šī‘ah, and the Islamization of the Malay-Indonesian Archipelago

Having observed the differences between the Sunni and *Šī‘ah* in terms *‘aqīdah*, we are now in a better position to locate the *ṭarīqah al-‘alawīyyah* in Shi‘i history and in the history of Islam in the Malay world.

The persecution of the descendants of the Prophet during Umayyah and Abbasiyyah times led to their retreat from political activism. One of the members of the House of the Prophet (*Ahl al-Bayt*), Imām Aḥmad ibn ‘Isā ibn Muḥammad ibn ‘Alī al-‘Uraydī ibn Ğa‘far al-Šādiq, also known as Aḥmad al-Muhāġir, left Basra as a result of persecution by the *Qarāmitah* in 317 h., with the aim of performing the *ḥaġġ* in Mecca.⁷ He was finally able to perform the *ḥaġġ* in 318/930, after which he went to Yemen with his second son ‘Ubaydallāh and two descendants of Imām Mūsā al-Kāzīm, Sālim ibn ‘Abdallāh and Muḥammad ibn Sulaymān.⁸

7 – al-Šātīrī, M.A., [Muḥammad Aḥmad ‘Umar al-Šātīrī], *Sīrat al-Salaf min Banī ‘Alawī al-Ḥusayniyyin*, Guddah, 1405 h. An Indonesian translation appears as *Sekilas Sejarah Salaf al-Alawiyin*, Pekalongan, 1986, p. 18; Serjeant, R.B., “The Sayids of Hadramawt”, in: *id.*, *Studies in Arabian History and Civilization*, London, 1981, p. 8; Wüstenfeld, F., *Die Čufiten in Süd-Arabien im XI. (XVII.) Jahrhundert*, Göttingen, 1883, p. 2-3.

8 – Sālim ibn ‘Abdallāh ibn al-Ḥusayn ibn ‘Alī ibn Adam ibn Idrīs ibn al-Ḥusayn ibn Muḥammad al-Ġawād ibn ‘Alī al-Riḍā ibn Mūsā al-Kāzīm, was the ancestor of the Banū Qudaym of Yemen. Muḥammad ibn Sulaymān ibn ‘Ubayd ibn ‘Isā ibn ‘Alawī ibn Muḥammad Ḥamḥām ibn ‘Awn ibn Mūsā al-Kāzīm, was the ancestor of the Banū Ahdal, also of Yemen. See Wüstenfeld, *Die Čufiten*, cit., p. 3, 6-7 and Table 1, no. 1-24.

Finally, in 340/952, Imām Aḥmad al-Muhāğir settled in Ḥaḍramawt which at that time, according to Hadhrami accounts, was dominated by the Ibadi. Imām Aḥmad, with the support of the inhabitants of Wādī Daw‘an, sympathizers of the *Ahl al-Bayt*, began the process of conversion of Ḥaḍramawt to the Shafi‘i school.⁹

Most Hadrami *Sādāt ‘ulamā’* maintain that Imām Aḥmad belonged to the Shafi‘i school.¹⁰ Nevertheless, there had been some debate in this century between ‘Alawī ibn Ṭāhir al-Ḥaddād, the Hadrami *muftī* of Johor and various historians of Saiwūn, Ḥaḍramawt, in which it was suggested that Aḥmad al-Muhāğir was an Imami *Šī‘ah*.¹¹ The fact that Imām Aḥmad was of the 8th generation from Imām ‘Alī and the 4th generation from Imām Ġa‘far al-Šādiq lends credence to this view. Since it was dangerous to hold Shi‘i views in an Ibadi-dominated area such as Ḥaḍramawt, it is possible that Shi‘i views were held under conditions of *taqiyyah* (dissimulation) while the Shafi‘i views were openly propagated. According to this reading, Imām Aḥmad disseminated the Shafi‘i school but had the historical consciousness of the *Šī‘ah*.

The grandson of Imām Aḥmad, ‘Alawī ibn ‘Ubaydallāh was the only one among his brothers Baṣrī and Ġadīd to leave male issue and it is he who gave his name to the clan of the Hadrami *Sādah*, variously known as *Banū ‘Alawī*, *Bā ‘Alawī*, or *Banū Sādah ‘alawiyyah*.¹²

‘*Alawiyyūn ‘ulamā’* divide the historical development of the ‘*Alawiyyūn* into four stages.¹³

During the first stage, which lasted from the third century to the seventh century h., ‘*Alawiyyūn* leaders such as Aḥmad al-Muhāğir and his grandson, ‘Alawī ibn ‘Ubaydallāh were *muğtahids* and carried the title of Imām. They were not followers of any particular *madḥab* or *ṭarīqah*. While it is true that a great deal of their *iğtihād* was in line with Imām Šāfi‘ī, this may have been partly due to the circumstances in Ḥaḍramawt at that time.

Having decided to lay down their arms and give up political struggle, the ‘*Alawiyyūn* became the carriers of a Sufi *ṭarīqah* when al-Ustād al-‘Azam Muḥammad al-Faqīh Muqaddam of the thirteenth generation from Imām ‘Alī obtained the *iğāzat al-ḥirqah* from Šayḥ Abū Madyan Šu‘ayb

9 – al-Šātiri, M.A. ‘U., *Adwār al-tārīḥ al-ḥaḍramī*, Ġuddah, 1392/1972, p. 160-162.

10 – al-Šātiri, *Adwār*, cit., p. 160.

11 – Serjeant, “The Sayids”, cit., p. 8-9.

12 – On the *nasab* (genealogy) of the Banū ‘Alawī see Saqqāf, ‘A. al-K., *Dirāsāt fi nasab al-Sādah Banī ‘Alawī: ḍuriyyat al-Imām al-Muhāğir Aḥmad ibn ‘Īsā*, Madīnah, 1989.

13 – Assyathiri, S.M.A. [Muḥammad Aḥmad ‘Umar al-Šātiri], *Sekilas Sejarah*, p. 21 ff.

ibn al-Ḥusayn.¹⁴ It is interesting to note that during this first stage the names Abū Bakr, ‘Umar and ‘Utmān were not given to the ‘*Alawiyyūn*.¹⁵ In the *silsilah* of Āl al-‘Attās, for example, the first time that any of these names appear is in 992h. when the first al-‘Attās, of the 27th generation from Imām ‘Alī, was named ‘Umar (‘Umar ibn ‘Abd al-Raḥmān ibn ‘Aqīl ibn Sālim ibn ‘Abdallāh ibn ‘Abd al-Raḥmān ibn ‘Abdallāh ibn ‘Abd al-Raḥmān al-Saqqāf). This had led some to suggest that the ‘*Alawiyyūn*, up until this time, were Shi‘i. In the opinion of Sayyid al-Ḥasan al-‘Attās, however, the reason for the absence of such names in some of the genealogies of the ‘*Alawiyyūn* has to do with the preference for names that occur earlier on in the *silsilah* resulting in other names not appearing for several generations. Among the descendants of Sayyidnā al-Ḥusayn ibn Abī Ṭālib one of the most frequently occurring names is ‘Alī. Sayyidnā al-Ḥusayn himself named three of his sons ‘Alī, that is, ‘Alī al-Akbar, ‘Alī Zayn al-‘Ābidīn and ‘Alī al-Aṣḡar.¹⁶ As a result, for several generations since the time of Sayyidnā al-Ḥusayn ibn Abī Ṭālib, the names such as Muḥammad, ‘Alī, al-Ḥusayn, al-Ḥasan, and ‘Alawī appear more frequently in some houses (*buyūt*) than others due to precedence established by a father or grandfather.

The second stage, then, is that of the development and consolidation of the *tarīqah al-‘alawiyyah*. This stage lasted from the seventh century to the eleventh century h.

The *tarīqah* is a simple one which does not stress *ḥalwah* but rather worldly activities while at the same time denouncing materialism. It may be referred to as a this-wordly *tarīqah* and is based on the simple formula of ‘ilm, ‘amal, *taḥallī*, *taḥallī*. It is the only order in which *nasab* and *tarīqah* come together, and this is where the importance of the Khaldunian concept of ‘*aṣabiyyah* is evident.

The third stage in the development of the ‘*Alawiyyūn* lasted from the 11th century to the 14th century h.. During this period, the ‘*Alawiyyūn* ‘*ulamā*’ and *awliyā*’ came to be known by the title of *ḥabīb*. This was the period of emigration to India and Southeast Asia.¹⁷

14 – On Šayḥ Abū Madyan see Cornell, V.J. (ed., trans.), *The Way of Abū Madyan: Doctrinal and Poetic Works of Abū Madyan Shu‘ayb ibn al-Husayn al-Anṣārī* (c.509/1115-16 - 594/1198), Cambridge [UK], 1996.

15 – al-Šātīrī, M.A. ‘U., *al-Mu‘ḡam al-laṭīf: li-asbāb al-alqāb wa ‘l-kunyā fi ‘l-nasab al-Šarīf li-qabā‘il wa buṭūn al-Sādah Banī ‘Alawī*, Ġuddah, 1406/1986, p. 43.

16 – al-Attas, S.H. [Sayyid Ḥasan Muḥammad Sālim al-‘Attās], *Umar bin Abdulrahman: Pengasas Ratib Al-Attas-Kisah dan Riwayat* [in Malay], Singapore, 1996, p. 106-108.

17 – Although Muḥammad Aḥmad al-Šātīrī dates the beginning of the third stage in the 11th century h., Hadrami emigration to India had begun much earlier. For overviews of Hadrami migration to India and Southeast Asia see Yusuf, A Talib [Yūsuf A Ṭālib], “Studies on the South Arabian Diaspora: Some Critical Remarks”, in: *Dio-genes*, 111 (1980).

For more than fifty years various theories have been presented as attempts at delineating the causes and modes of conversion to Islam as well as the consequences of the coming of Islam to the Malay-Indonesian archipelago.¹⁸ Many authors stressed the fact that Islam was brought to the region by traders from Arabia, Persia, India and China. Although it was clearly through trade that Islam was initially introduced into the archipelago it is extremely doubtful that the large-scale conversions to Islam can be explained simply in terms of these early trading contacts. Theories that suggest other modes of conversion to Islam need to be considered. These theories explain large-scale conversion in terms of economic and political motives, rivalry between the Muslims and Portuguese, inter-marriages, and Sufi proselytization.

It was van Leur, among others, who stressed the significance of political factors in the islamization of Indonesia. His reading was that Islam was adopted as a political instrument against Indian trade, Siam, China, and the Hindu Majapahit regime in Java.¹⁹ Several objections can be made to this view. One is that even if it was established that rulers in general converted to Islam for political and economic reasons, one cannot leap to the conclusion that the whole archipelago did so for the same reasons. Also, if the logic of conversion for economic and political reasons was operating, why were there no conversions to Chinese religion during the thirteenth to the sixteenth centuries when China was a regional power in the archipelago?²⁰

Schrieke had discussed the conversion to Islam in terms of Muslim-Portuguese antagonism in the archipelago. Although he was fully aware that the large-scale conversions to Islam began in the thirteenth century,²¹ that is, before Portuguese dominance, he nevertheless insisted that it is "impossible to understand the spread of Islam in the archipelago unless one takes into account the antagonism between the Moslem traders and the Portuguese".²²

The theory that the conversion of the archipelago resulted from inter-marriages between members of royal and merchant families received special attention by Harrison who referred to the ability of the marriage institution to spread Islam from Malakka to the north in Pahang and Kedah,

18 – For critical accounts of these theories see Alatas, S.H. [Sayyid Ḥusayn al-‘Attās], "Reconstruction of Malaysian History", in: *Revue de Sud-est Asiatique*, 3 (1962), p. 219-245; Al-Attas, S.M.N [Sayyid Muḥammad Naqīb al-‘Attās], *Preliminary Statement on a General Theory of the Islamization of the Malay-Indonesian Archipelago*, Kuala Lumpur, 1969; Alatas, S.F [Sayyid Farid al-‘Attās], "Notes on Various Theories Regarding the Islamization of the Malay Archipelago", in: *Muslim World*, 75, 3-4 (1985), p. 162-175; Fatimi, S.Q., *Islam Comes to Malaysia*, Singapore, 1963.

19 – Leur, van J.C., *Indonesian Trade and Society*, The Hague, 1955, p. 112.

20 – Alatas, "Reconstruction", cit., p. 237.

21 – Schrieke, B., *Indonesian Sociological Studies*, II, The Hague, 1957, p. 231.

22 – *Ibid.*, p. 233.

and to the south in Sumatra.²³ Before Harrison, Veth had referred to the marriage factor in the advent of Islam in the archipelago.²⁴ This view of islamization seems rather unconvincing as there were only a relatively small number of foreign Muslim merchants who had settled in the Malay-Indonesian archipelago during the period under consideration. They were sporadically settled along coastal areas and mostly transient.²⁵ While inter-marriage was probably a means of islamization, it would only explain conversions in the coastal areas.

The view that Sufism was responsible for the conversion of Indonesia to Islam was propounded by Johns. He pointed out that the Sufi "interpretation of Islam was certainly suited to the background of the Indonesians..." and that the "conversion of Indonesia to Islam was very largely the work of the *tarikas* even though they are ungratefully spurned at the present day".²⁶ While it is very true that Sufis were involved in the proselytization of Islam in the archipelago, there is little mention of the *tariqah al-'alawiyyah* in this respect, although the role of the Hadrami Arabs in the islamization of the region is well-known. Works that discuss islamization had generally neglected the contribution of this community in the conversion of Southeast Asia to Islam. The view that Islam had spread in the archipelago largely as a result of marriages between royal and merchant families, or as a consequence of Sufi missionary activities, is mere speculation or, at best, incomplete unless supported by empirical studies on the histories and genealogies of the various Hadrami Arab as well as Indian Muslim families, many of which were assimilated into the indigenous societies in the archipelago. Hadrami Arab and Indian Muslim traders had been engaging in trade and missionary activities in the region for centuries and constituted an integral part of the Muslim trade diaspora which stretched from Egypt to the Malay world.

In the last century, European scholars had held that islamization was brought about as a result of direct contact with Arab traders, a thesis which was first rejected by the Dutch scholar Pijnappel.²⁷ Pijnappel ascribed the spread of Islam in the region to the work of Arabs from Gujerat and Malabar.²⁸ After Pijnappel, it was Snouck Hurgronje who developed the view of islamization from India.

23 - Harrison, B., *South-East Asia: A Short History*, London, 1954, p. 50-51, 56-57.

24 - Veth, P.J., *Java, Geografisch, Etnologisch, Historisch*, Harlem, 1896-1907.

25 - Schrieke, *Indonesian*, II, cit., p. 231.

26 - Johns, A.H., "Muslim Mystics and Historical Writing", in: Hall, D.G.E. (ed.), *Historians of Southeast Asia*, London, 1961, p. 40-41.

27 - Pijnappel, J., "Over de Kennis, die de Arabieren voor de Komst der Portugeezen van den Indischen Archipel Bezaten", in: *Bijdragen tot de Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde*, 7 (1972), p. 135-158.

28 - Pijnappel, "Over de Kennis", cit., p. 157-158.

In a lecture on Arabia and the Netherlands Indies delivered at Leiden University in 1907, Snouck asserted that the view that colonies of Arab traders were established in Java and Sumatra before the 16th century was incorrect.²⁹ Here Snouck suggests that all things of Arab origin that made their way to the Malay archipelago passed through India and that Islam was introduced to the region through the intermediation of India.³⁰ Decisive Arab influence as far as the spread of Islam in the Malay world is concerned was only after the 16th century and this came out of Ḥadramawt in South Arabia and Mecca.³¹ The Hadrami influence in Southeast Asia is, of course, evident from the large numbers of Hadrami settlers who have become permanent additions to the demographic landscape of the Malay world.

Earlier, in 1883, Snouck proposed the thesis of the South Indian origins of Indonesian Islam but, as Drewes pointed out, fails to identify the region of South India from where these proselytizers came.³² In addition to this, Snouck did not specify the region in Arabia that the Arabs, coming via India, originated from.

The large-scale islamization of the Malay-Indonesian archipelago which began in the 14th century was carried out by Indians as well as by Indians of Arab origin and Arabs who came to the region via India. The Indo-Arab origins of Islam in Southeast Asia must be understood in the context of the modes of conversion such as trade, marriage, and the role of the Sufi *ṭariqahs*. What has been conspicuously absent in the literature on the history of Islam in Southeast Asia, especially with regard to the period in question, is recognition of the role of the Hadrami *ṭariqah al-'alawīyyah* in the process of conversion. In other words, the question of who were the Arabs who traded, intermarried, and established *ṭariqahs* in the region comes to mind. A prominent case in point is that of the so-called legend of the nine saints (Jav. *wali songo*) of Java.

The *Babad Tanah Jawi*, a generic title referring to several Javanese manuscripts, attributes the conversion of Java to the work of the *wali*

29 – Snouck Hurgronje, C., “L’Arabie et les Indes Néerlandaises”, in: *Verspreide Geschriften van C. Snouck Hurgronje: Deel IV - Geschriften Betreffende den Islam in Nederlandsch-Indie (Tweede Reeks)*, Bonn & Leipzig, 1924, p. 105.

30 – Snouck Hurgronje, “L’Arabie”, cit., p. 106.

31 – Snouck Hurgronje, “L’Arabie”, cit., p. 109-110.

32 – Drewes, G.W.J., “New Light on the Coming of Islam to Indonesia?”, in: *Bi-jdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, 124 (1968), p. 441. There is some literature on the South Indian Muslim population and their long-standing contact with the Arabs which suggest the parts of South India that are of relevance to us. See D’Souza, V.S., “Social Organization and Marriage Customs of the Moplahs on the South-west Coast of India”, in: *Anthropos*, 54 (1959), p. 487-516 and D’Souza, “Status Groups among the Moplahs on the South-west Coast of India”, in: Ahmad, I. (ed.), *Caste and Social Stratification among Muslims in India*, New Delhi, 1978, p. 41-56.

songo.³³ These manuscripts contain some historical records but are, for the most part, legendary accounts on the islamization of Java. The accounts of the nine saints are usually couched in fantastic terms with descriptions of their magical powers. This had led many scholars to regard the legends more as insights into how the Indonesians viewed the process of islamization rather than as historical records of conversion to Islam.³⁴ In some cases, the specific Hadrami origins appear to be unknown to some authors. For example, Raffles refers to some of the *walīs* as originating from Arabia but does not refer to their Hadrami origins nor to the fact that they were settled in India prior to coming to Southeast Asia.³⁵ Arnold refers to one of the *walīs*, Malik Ibrāhīm, as a descendant of a grandson of the Prophet, Zayn al-‘Ābidīn and a cousin of the Raja of Chermen.³⁶ According to Veth, Chermen is located in India while Rouffaer places it in Sumatra.³⁷ Majul refers to these *walīs* as being Indians or Arabs originating from Arab settlements in India.³⁸ Indonesian works, however, know these *walīs* to be historical personalities.³⁹ Furthermore, Hadrami sources contain the genealogies⁴⁰ of these *walīs* who lived in Java during the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries. It is from these genealogies that it is known that many were Hadrami Arabs who had come to the Malay archipelago via India. The names of the *walīs* of whom there were more than nine can be listed as follows:⁴¹

33 – Ramlan M. (trans.), *Babad Tanah Jawi*, Kuala Lumpur, 1975. This is a Malay translation of the original Javanese text.

34 – Johns, A.H., “Islam in Southeast Asia: Reflections and New Directions”, in: *Indonesia*, 19 (1975), p. 42; Ricklefs, M.C., *History of Modern Indonesia*, Houndmills, 1981, p. 10-11.

35 – Raffles, T.S., *The History of Java*, Kuala Lumpur, 1965, p. 113, 117.

36 – Arnold, T.W., *The Preaching of Islam: A History of the Propagation of the Muslim Faith*, London, 1913, p. 378. Imām ‘Alī Zayn al-‘Ābidīn was actually of the fourth generation from the Prophet Muḥammad (peace be upon Him).

37 – Veth, *Java*, cit., I, p. 230. Cited in Arnold, *The Preaching of Islam: A History of the Propagation of the Muslim Faith*, p. 378; Rouffaer, G.P., “Het Tijdperk van Godsdienstovergang (1400-1600) in den Maleischen Archipel”, in: *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, 50 (1899), p. 115 n.

38 – Majul, C.A., “Theories on the Introduction and Expansion of Islam in Malaysia”, in: *International Association of the Historians of Asia, 2nd Biennial Conference Proceedings*, 1962, p. 363.

39 – See, for example, Salam, S., *Sekitar Walisanga*, np, Penerbit Menara Kudus, nd; Lembaga Research Islam (Pesantren Luhur Islam Sunan Giri), *Sejarah dan Da'wah Islamiyah Sunan Giri*, Surabaya, 1975 (in Indonesian).

40 – al-Saqqāf, A. ‘A. al-‘A., *Ḥidmat al-‘ašīrah*, Jakarta, 1384/1964. See also Chehab, T. [Tāriq Šahāb], *Asal-usul Para Wali, Susuhunan, Sultan, Dsb, di Indonesia*, Jakarta, 1975 [in Indonesian].

41 – Indonesian local names are given in parenthesis.

1. al-Imām Ğamāl al-Dīn al-Ḥusayn ibn al-Amīr Aḥmad Šāh Ğalāl ibn al-Amīr ‘Abdallāh Ḥān ibn ‘Abd al-Malik ibn ‘Alawī ‘Amm al-Faqīh ibn Muḥammad Šāḥib Marbāt ibn ‘Alī Ḥalī‘ Qasam ibn ‘Alawī ibn Muḥammad ibn ‘Alawī ibn ‘Ubayd Allāh ibn Aḥmad al-Muhāğir ibn ‘Isā ibn Muḥammad al-Naqīb ibn ‘Alī al-‘Uraydī ibn Ğa‘far al-Šādiq ibn Muḥammad al-Bāqir ibn ‘Alī Zayn al-‘Ābidīn ibn al-Ḥusayn al-Sibt ibn al-Imām ‘Alī ibn Abī Ṭalīb Karamallāh Wağḥuh⁴² (Wajuk Makasar).

2. Ibrāhīm Zayn al-Dīn al-Akbar ibn al-Imām Ğamāl al-Dīn al-Ḥusayn⁴³ (Sunan Nnggesik of Tuban).

3. Aḥmad Raḥmat Allāh Šāḥib Ampel ibn Ibrāhīm Zayn al-Dīn al-Akbar⁴⁴ (Sunan Ampel of Surabaya).

4. ‘Alī Murtaḍā ibn Ibrāhīm Zayn al-Dīn al-Akbar⁴⁵ (Raden Santri of Gresik).

5. Mawlānā Ishāq ibn Ibrāhīm Zayn al-Dīn al-Akbar.⁴⁶

6. Muḥammad ‘Ayn al-Yaqīn Šāḥib Giri ibn Mawlānā Ishāq⁴⁷ (Sunan Giri of Gresik).

7. Ibrāhīm Šāḥib al-Tuban ibn Aḥmad Raḥmat Allāh Šāḥib Ampel⁴⁸ (Sunan Bonang of Tuban).

8. Aḥmad Ḥisām ibn Aḥmad Raḥmat Allāh Šāḥib Ampel.⁴⁹

9. Ğa‘far al-Šādiq Šāḥib al-Quds ibn Aḥmad Raḥmat Allāh Šāḥib Ampel⁵⁰ (Sunan Kudus).

10. Zayn al-‘Ābidīn Šāḥib Demak ibn Aḥmad Raḥmat Allāh Šāḥib Ampel⁵¹ (of Demak).

11. Hāšim Šāḥib Darāğat ibn Aḥmad Raḥmat Allāh Šāḥib Ampel⁵² (Sunan Darajat of Lamongan).

12. Hidāyat Allāh ibn ‘Abdallāh ibn ‘Alī Nūr al-‘Ālam ibn al-Imām Ğamāl al-Dīn al-Ḥusayn⁵³ (Sunan Gunung Jati of Cirebon).

13. Ḥasan al-Dīn ibn Hidāyat Allāh.⁵⁴

42 – al-Saqqāf, *Ḥidmat*. The link to Aḥmad al-Muhāğir confirms the Hadrami origins of Ğamāl al-Dīn al-Ḥusayn, from whom many of the “legendary” *walīs* of Indonesia originate.

43 – al-Saqqāf, *Ḥidmat*.

44 – *Ibid*.

45 – *Ibid*.

46 – al-Saqqāf, *Ḥidmat*; Lembaga Research Islam, *Sejarah*, p. 64.

47 – al-Saqqāf, *Ḥidmat*.

48 – *Ibid*.

49 – *Ibid*.

50 – *Ibid*.

51 – al-Saqqāf, *Ḥidmat*. Chehab [Šahāb] in *Asal-usul* has Zayn al-‘Ābidīn as the son of Aḥmad Ḥisām (p. 16), which is incorrect as far the *Ḥidmat al-‘asīrah* is concerned.

52 – al-Saqqāf, *Ḥidmat*.

53 – *Ibid*. ‘Abdallāh and his father, ‘Alī Nūr al-‘Ālam established themselves in Campa and Siam, respectively.

14. al-Malik Ibrāhīm ibn Barakat Zayn al-‘Ālam ibn al-Imām Ğamāl al-Dīn al-Ḥusayn⁵⁵ (of Gapura).

In addition to the above, Chehab lists Bāb Allāh ibn ‘Abdallāh ibn ‘Alī Nūr al-‘Ālam ibn al-Imām Ğamāl al-Dīn al-Ḥusayn⁵⁶ but the *Ḥidmat al-‘Ašīrah* does not list Bāb Allāh in this genealogy.

The link of the *wali songo* to Aḥmad al-Muhāġir confirms their Hadrami origins. Nevertheless, some would claim that the Hadrami *sayyid* origin of the *wali songo* is a fabricated reconstruction.⁵⁷ Such a position is probably due to a lack of familiarity with earlier Hadrami sources, that is, those that are more or less contemporaneous with the *wali songo* themselves. The *Ḥidmat al-‘Ašīrah* itself is a twentieth century document but is based on a variety of earlier sources such as the *Šams al-zahīrah* (1307/1889-1890) of ‘Abd al-Rahmān ibn Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥusayn al-Maš-hūr; *Umdat al-ṭālib fi ansāb Āl Abī Ṭālib* of Aḥmad ibn ‘Alī ibn al-Ḥusayn; *al-Ġurar* of Muḥammad ibn ‘Alī ibn ‘Alawī Ḥird al-Ḥusaynī al-‘Alawī al-Tarīmī (d. 960h.).

The question of Hadrami origins is important not merely for the sake of historical accuracy but because it laid the foundations for the *ṭarīqah* which was firmly established by Hadramis later and partly explains the Shi‘i tendencies to be found in Indonesia today.

There are a number of derivatives of the *ṭarīqah al-‘alawīyyah* such as the *‘aydrusiyyah ṭā‘ifah* founded by Abū Bakr ibn ‘Abdallāh al-‘Aydrūs (d. 914/1509) in Tarīm which spread to East Africa, India and Indonesia. There is also the *ṭarīqah al-‘attāsiyyah* which established itself in the Indian sub-continent and Burma.

Elements of Shi‘i Culture in Indonesia

Any discussion on the presence of Shi‘i Islam in Southeast Asia must distinguish between the Shi‘i school of jurisprudence on the one hand and Shi‘i culture on the other. To be sure, both are found although there are differences in their genesis and development. While the vast majority of Indonesian Muslims belong to the *Šāfi‘ī madhāb* aspects of *Šī‘ah* Islam can be found in their culture and mores, these having been implanted in the region centuries ago. It is only in this century, particularly after the Iranian revolution of 1978, that there has been a consciousness and awareness of the *Šī‘ah* and their history, which was sometimes accompanied by “conversion” to the Shi‘i school, but more often resulted in the study and

54 – *Ibid.*

55 – *Ibid.*

56 – Chehab, *Asal-usul*, cit., p. 15.

57 – See, for example, Bruinessen, van M., “Najmuddin al-Kubra and Jamaluddin al-Akbar: Traces of Kubrawīya Influence in Early Indonesian Islam”, in: *Bijdragen to de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 150, 2 (1994), p. 326.

spread of Shi'i teachings without necessarily involving a change in *madhab*. The rise of the Shi'i *madhab* in Indonesia and Malaysia will be taken up in the next section. For now, I wish to enumerate the aspects of Shi'i culture to be found in Indonesia. In this connection two points should be noted.

One, the vast majority of Indonesians are unaware of the presence of Shi'i customs and norms in their practice of Islam.

Two, the Shi'i influences in Indonesian Islam are both the result of direct contact with Shi'i communities in India and West Asia as well as the 'Alawiyyūn factor in the islamization of the Malay world.

The Shi'i customs to be found in Indonesia can be listed as follows:

1. The commemoration of 'āšūrā' (Ind. *perayaan asyura*), on the anniversary of the martyrdom of Imām al-Ḥusayn at Karbalā'.⁵⁸ This takes place in Aceh, Palembang, Minangkabau, Bengkulu and includes a procession of the *tābūt* of al-Ḥusayn, drawn in procession by an ornately designed catafalque.⁵⁹ This ceremony resembles that of the *ta'ziyah* of Iran and the subcontinent.

2. 'Āšūrā' porridge. Known as *bubur suran* in Java and *kanji acura* in Sunda, this porridge is made from rice and other cereals with coconut milk and is offered to neighbours during the month of *muḥarram*.⁶⁰

3. Various literary works give a special place to Imām 'Alī and his family. For example, in the *Hikayat Raja Khandaq*, 'Alī is aided in battle by the angle Ġibrīl. In the *Hikayat Mohammad Hanafiyah*, Muḥammad Ibn al-Ḥanafiyah dreams that the Prophet orders him to revenge the deaths of al-Ḥasan and al-Ḥusayn.⁶¹

4. The lavishly decorated tombs (*maqām*) and the practice of *ziyārah* is seen as more as an element of Ši'ah Islam that found its way into Indonesia.⁶²

These Shi'i elements in Indonesia are possibly a result of Shi'i influence from West Asia as well as India. They are also a result of the influence of the 'Alawiyyūn in Indonesia.⁶³ The *madhab* of the 'Alawiyyūn, though formally Shafi'i, is also referred to as *madhab Ahl al-Bayt* because of the genealogical link of the practitioners of the *ṭarīqah al-'alawiyyah* with the Prophet (peace be upon Him). Nevertheless, it is incor-

58 - al-Baqir, M., [Muḥammad al-Bāqir], "Pengantar Tentang Kaum Alawiyyin", in: Haddad, A. [ʿAbdallāh al-Ḥaddād], *Ṭarīqah Menuju Kegahagiaan*, Bandung, 1986, p. 51 [in Indonesian].

59 - Baried, B., "Le Shi'isme en Indonésie", in: *Archipel*, 15 (1978), p. 77. See also, Roedjati Soemardjito, S. W., "Tjerita Tabut", in: *Bahasa dan Budaya*, IX, 3-4, p. 81-89 [in Indonesian].

60 - Baried, "Le Shi'isme", cit., p. 76-77.

61 - For more examples and details see Baried, "Le Shi'isme", cit., p. 77-79.

62 - al-Baqir, "Pengantar", cit., p. 51.

63 - *Ibid.*

rect to say that the *'Alawiyyūn*, including the *wali songo*, introduced *Šī'ah* Islam to Indonesia, as suggested by some,⁶⁴ because the *'Alawiyyūn* have always been strict Shafī'is, regardless of their Shi'i scent (Indo. *bau Syi'ah*).

The Rise of the Imami Shi'i Among the 'Alawiyyūn

It has already been mentioned that there are Shi'i tendencies among the *'Alawiyyūn*, the main reason for this being the genealogical convergence between the *'Alawiyyūn* and the *Šī'ah*.

So far we have said nothing of the actual practices of the *Imāmī* or *Ġa'farī madhab* among the *'Alawiyyūn*. This is something that took place in the fourth stage of the development of the *'Alawiyyūn* which began in the 14th century h., that is, the period of acculturation and assimilation in the Malay world of Southeast Asia.

The actual "conversion" to *Šī'ah* Islam took place generally after the Iranian revolution of 1979. Nevertheless, throughout the history of the *'Alawiyyūn* there have been instances of practioners of *Šī'ah* Islam both among the *wilāyati* and the *muwalladūn*.

One *'alawī* scholar, about whom it is uncertain as to what extent he was a *Šī'ah*, was Muḥammad ibn 'Aqīl al-'Alawī (1863-1931) of the al-Yahyà house.⁶⁵

Muḥammad ibn 'Aqīl was born in Ḥaḍramawt in Masīlah 'Alī Šayḥ, lived part of his life in Singapore where he did some writing, and finally settled in al-Ḥudaydah, Yemen. He had written a number of historical works on the early history of the *Šī'ah*, some of which were published in Iran and some in Jakarta.

Worth mentioning in this connection is Sayyid Abū Bakr ibn 'Abd al-Rahmān ibn Šahāb of Tarīm, Ḥaḍramawt whose writings were in defense of Muḥammad ibn 'Aqīl's views and of *Šī'ah* Islam in general.⁶⁶

Nevertheless, it has been mainly among the *muwalladūn*, particularly in Malaysia and Indonesia, that we have a renewed interest in *Šī'ah* Islam. There are three major reasons for which this happened.

One is the self-perceived general lack of development among the *'Alawiyyūn* with respect to the other religious and ethnic communities of Southeast Asia.⁶⁷

64 - al-Amin, H. (ed.), *Dā'irat al-ma'ārif al-islāmiyyah al-šī'iyyah*, Eng. trans. *Islamic Shi'ite Encyclopaedia*, I, p. 42; D. Sirajuddin AR & Iqbal Abdurrauf Saimima, "Yang di Sini, Syi'ah Gado-Gado, Pak", *Panji Masyarakat*, 513 (August, 1986), p. 20 [in Indonesian].

65 - Ende, W., "Schiitische Tendenzen bei Sunnitischen Sayyids aus Hadhramaut: Muhammad ibn 'Aqil al-'Alawi (1863-1931)", in: *Der Islam*, 50 (1973), p. 82-97.

66 - See *Ruṣfat al-sādī fi baḥr faqā'il Banī al-Nabī al-Hādī*, al-Qāhirah, 1303 h.

67 - Assyathiri, *Sekilas*, cit., p. 59-61.

Another was the Iranian revolution of 1979 and the heightened awareness of neo-colonialism, and cultural dependency that it brought.

Thirdly, and just as crucial was the fact that the leader who emerged in the revolution, Imām Khumaynī, was a *Sayyid* himself. It was at this time that the genealogical convergence between the *Imāmī Šī'ī madhhab* and the *'Alawiyyūn* became apparent to the *'Alawiyyūn* of Indonesia and Malaysia. It was therefore in the 1980s that interest in *Šī'ī fiqh* and *uṣūl al-fiqh, falsafah, 'ilm al-kalām*, and social thought developed. This is reflected in religious education in the *madrrasah*, as well as in informal education (*mağlis al-ta'lim*, Malay/Indo. *pengajian*) and in the range of books translated from Arabic and Persian as well as original works written in Malay and Indonesian.

Nevertheless, the renewed interest in *Šī'ah* Islam does not necessarily take the form of "conversion" to the *Šī'ī madhhab*. In fact five different orientations among the *'Alawiyyūn* to *Šī'ah* Islam can be discerned:⁶⁸

1. Anti-*Šī'ah*. These are a minority who are not only strict Shafi'is by conviction and practice, but who regard the *Šī'ah* as having strayed from the True Path and are not considered as being on an equal footing with the four Sunni *madāhib*. These are views that are held by quite a number of non-*'Alawiyyūn* in Southeast Asia as well and have attracted some attention in the media. A case in point is the work of Ustaz Ashaari Muhammad of the now banned Arqam organization in Malaysia. He referred to the Iranian revolution as not a revolution of Islam, but a revolution of the *Šī'ah* and holds the view that the *Šī'ah* are politically strong in Iran because they "sell the name of Islam".⁶⁹ The book discusses various aspects of the "deviations" of the *Šī'ah*. There are also statements in the media expressing concern over the "*Šī'ah* threat" and questioning the *'aqidah* of the *Šī'ah*.⁷⁰

2. The Ja'fari school as the fifth *madhhab*. The majority of the *'Alawiyyūn* see the *Imāmī Šī'ah* as belonging to a fifth *madhhab* which is seen to be on an equal footing with the four Sunni schools.

3. Shafi'is with Shi'i sympathies. This group is very interesting in that they believe in following the Shafi'i school as far as the *'ibādah* is con-

68 – The following is a rather sketchy account as no printed material is available on the topic. Participant observation and interviews are currently being carried out to elaborate on the discussion presented here.

69 – Ashaari, M., *Bahaya Syiah (The Šī'ah Danger)*, Kuala Lumpur, 1987, p. V-VI [in Malay].

70 – Suhaimi, M., "Syiah: Mencabar Akidah Umat Islam" ["Shi'a: Challenging the *'aqidah* of the Muslim *ummah*"], in: *al-Islam*, 20, 232 (April, 1993), p. 10-12 [in Malay]; Sani, F. M., "Mungkinkah Syiah Terkeluar Daripada Islam?" ["Are the *Šī'ah* Out of Islam?"], in: *al-Islam*, 20, 232, (April, 1993) [in Malay], p. 8-9; "Pensyarah Sebar Faham Syiah" ["Lecturer Spreads *Šī'ī* Teachings"], in: *Berita Minggu*, 25 February, 1990 [in Malay]; "Ajaran Syiah Boleh Jejas Perpaduan" ["Shi'i Teachings Could Damage Unity"], *Berita Harian*, 3 March, 1990 [in Malay].

cerned, in line with the teachings and practice of the *ağdād* (ancestors), but they are one with the *Šī'ah* with regards to historical consciousness, especially when it comes to the interpretation of early Muslim history, the events of the Saqāfah, the tragedy of Karbalā', and so on. They also approach the question of the validity of *ḥadīth* with the same caution that the *Šī'ah* do. In fact, they regard the *ṭarīqah al-'alawīyyah* to be the way of the *Ahl al-Bayt* as much as the Ja'fari school is. The fact that the one follows Imām Šāfi'ī and the other Imām Ġa'far al-Šādiq is not an issue of consequence as far as *īmān* and *iḥsān* are concerned.

4. *'Alawīyyūn Šī'ah*. These are the *'Alawīyyūn* who have made the total switch to the Shi'ī school in term of *'ibādah* as well as worldview. They take the position that the *madḥab* of the *Ahl al-Bayt* can only be the Ja'fari school and no other and that it is better (*aḡḍal*) for the *'Alawīyyūn* as descendants of the Prophet, to be direct followers of Imām Ġa'far al-Šādiq. Nevertheless, these "converts" retain the customs and mores of the Hadrami *'Alawīyyūn* for the most part.

5. Anti-*'Alawīyyūn Šī'ah*. This is a minority who no longer maintain the appearance of the being *'Alawīyyūn* in terms of the acts of worship and culture. For example, they do not attend the Friday noon prayer, they do not participate in the weekly *rāṭib* sessions and read, instead, the *du'ā kumayl*, and they consider *zafīn* (a Hadrami dance) as a prohibited (*ḥarām*) practice in Islam. It was even reported that members of this group were of the opinion that those *'Alawīyyūn 'ulamā'* who did not pass out of Shi'ī centres of learning, should not be given the respect that is normally accorded to the *'Alawīyyūn*, such as the kissing of the hands.

As far as the development of *Šī'ah* Islam in Indonesia is concerned, it is the third and fourth groups that are the most important. Each group operates according to a different logic of argumentation in their debates with each other. The third group is more concerned with the social consequences of school switching while the fourth group is preoccupied with the juridical question of following the "right" *madḥab*. For the Shafi'ī with Shi'ī sympathies, while all the schools of jurisprudence are equal and legitimate, the social consequences of switching from one to another may be adverse in the sense that it results in highlighting differences in daily religious practices that were previously not there. In fact, many *'Alawīyyūn* families are split between Shafi'ī and Shi'ī "factions" characterised by protracted social conflicts, some more benign than others.

This list of orientations towards *Šī'ah* Islam only scratches the surface of the process of "conversion" and reaction to the school and worldview and is the basis of more elaborate work which is on-going.